

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF THE LETTER OF CREDIT SYSTEM IN INTERNATIONAL TRADE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19971694>

Abstract. *International commerce includes a wide range of transactional operations that arise between business partners - individuals and entities – located in different places. This is related to economic and legal risks to much extent. A letter of credit, which is also referred as to a documentary credit, is one of the important tools of payment methods over the globe. This paper examines not only the legal nature, role and importance of the system Letter of Credit (L/C) in the global market, but also potential reduction of non-payment situations and introduction of guarantees for importer and exporters. The specific system under the UCP 600 for international L/C operations is given the unique focus while discussing the mechanism of resolving disputes arising from international letter of credit operations. Moreover, the advantages of using documentary credits, the reason of prioritization of L/C over other payment methods are analyzed, at the same time some limited operations while issuing documentary credits, particularly the standard of strict compliance and the principle of independence of L/C from the main contract between parties who ask to issue a credit, are criticized throughout the paper.*

Аннотация. *Международная торговля включает в себя широкий спектр транзакционных операций, возникающих между деловыми партнерами — физическими и юридическими лицами, — расположенными в разных местах. Это в значительной степени связано с экономическими и правовыми рисками. Аккредитив, также называемый документарным аккредитивом, является одним из важных инструментов платежных систем во всем мире. В данной статье рассматривается не только правовая природа, роль и значение системы аккредитивов (АК) на мировом рынке, но и потенциальное снижение числа случаев неплатежей и введение гарантий для импортеров и экспортеров. Особое внимание уделяется специфической системе в рамках UCP 600 для международных операций с аккредитивами, а также обсуждается механизм разрешения споров, возникающих в связи с международными операциями с аккредитивами. Кроме того, анализируются преимущества использования документарных аккредитивов, причины приоритета аккредитивов перед другими методами платежей, а также критикуются некоторые ограничения при выдаче документарных аккредитивов, в частности, стандарт строгого соблюдения и принцип независимости аккредитива от основного договора между сторонами, запрашивающими аккредитив.*

Annotatsiya. *Xalqaro savdo turli joylarda joylashgan biznes hamkorlar - jismoniy va yuridik shaxslar - o'rtasida yuzaga keladigan keng ko'lamli tranzaksiya operatsiyalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Bu ko'p jihatdan iqtisodiy va huquqiy xavflar bilan bog'liq. Hujjatli akkreditiv deb ham ataladigan akkreditiv butun dunyo bo'ylab to'lov usullarining muhim vositalaridan biridir.*

Ushbu maqolada nafaqat akkreditiv tizimining (AK) global bozordagi huquqiy tabiati, roli va ahamiyati, balki to'lovlarni amalga oshirmaslik holatlarini kamaytirish va import qiluvchilar va eksportchilar uchun kafolatlarni joriy etish imkoniyatlari ham ko'rib chiqiladi.

Xalqaro akkreditiv operatsiyalari uchun UCP 600 bo'yicha maxsus tizimga xalqaro akkreditiv operatsiyalaridan kelib chiqadigan nizolarni hal qilish mexanizmi muhokama qilinayotganda alohida e'tibor qaratiladi.

Bundan tashqari, hujjatli akkreditivlardan foydalanishning afzalliklari, akkreditivning boshqa to'lov usullariga nisbatan ustuvorligining sababi tahlil qilinadi, shu bilan birga hujjatli akkreditivlarni berishda ba'zi cheklangan operatsiyalar, xususan, qat'iy rioya qilish standartlari va akkreditivning akkreditiv berishni so'ragan tomonlar o'rtasidagi asosiy shartnomadan mustaqilligi prinsipi maqola davomida tanqid qilinadi.

Keywords: *Letter of Credit (L/C), Documentary Credit, International Trade, Trade Finance, Payment Security, Risk Management, Banking System, UCP 600, Export and Import, Financial Instruments, Commercial Transactions, Bank Guarantee, Trust in Trade, Global Commerce.*

Ключевые слова: *аккредитив (L/C), документарный аккредитив, международная торговля, торговое финансирование, обеспечение платежей, управление рисками, банковская система, UCP 600, экспорт и импорт, финансовые инструменты, коммерческие сделки, банковская гарантия, доверие в торговле, глобальная торговля.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Akkreditiv (L/C), hujjatli kredit, xalqaro savdo, savdoni moliyalashtirish, to'lov xavfsizligi, risklarni boshqarish, bank tizimi, UCP 600, eksport va import, moliyaviy instrumentlar, tijorat operatsiyalari, bank kafolati, savdo ishonchi, global savdo.*

Introduction

International trade is one of the main components of global economy and includes the complex commercial operations that may take place between exporters and importers located in different countries. These are mostly related to economic and legal phenomenon, such as the process of non-payment, fraud, and breach of a contract as mentioned above. That is why in global trade it is claimed that there is a huge need for reliable and safe mechanisms of payment.

Based on this need, the L/C system has been developed as one of the most important financial instruments. As customs, the way international payments are made varies from country to country. The decision about suitability is determined by several factors: the market, the amount of money to be paid, the country, the level of understanding and trust between the two parties, the commercial practices associated with a particular line of business, the various restrictions and regulations of the country where the payment has to be made, and the costs involved in selling the goods. There are several ways of payment, including a payment into an open account, cheque, draft, guarantee of payment issued by a bank, Documentary Collections, Letter of credit (L/C). It is widely considered that The Letter of Credit (L/C) is the safest method of payment when making it internationally¹. That is why this system deserves an extra focus for a further research. A letter of credit is a payment guarantee given by banks and it guarantees to make the agreed payment only when the required documents are complied with the rules of review by banks to a seller. This serves to strengthen particular trust between parties and make transnational commercial operations safe. Documentary credit-related operations are regulated by the globally accepted custom-rules – UCP 600 – “Uniform customs and practice for documentary credits”. These rules standardize the process of issuing the L/Cs by banks and underlines the principle of working with documents, which is discussed further later.

Discussion and results

Before going deep into the main points, it should be discussed what the L/C is and what its nature is.

¹ Wevers, H. (2021). *A basic guide to international business law* (5th ed.). Routledge.

As mentioned above letter of Credit (LC) is one of the important parts of international trade which ensures security, trust and convenience for both parties who are bound with different commercial contracts.

It is argued that improvements in commercial transactions cannot be imagined without proper working system of Letter of Credits, which is also named Documentary credits most of the time. The reason why this payment method is specifically used is not only about convenient atmosphere for Entrepreneurs in business transactions, but also emergence of huge positive prospects for the growth of international commerce, globalization, unified resources from different states which can later work for further developments in documentary credit system. The existence of a whole certain part of legal system on this basis itself shows more about the importance of L/C. What is claimed here is that every single process in the field of law emerges just because business people; individuals or legal entities need it in certain relations.

In another word, “a letter of credit is a promise to pay”². The LC process is initiated when the buyer and seller enter into a sales contract in which payment by Letter of Credit is agreed. If in sales or other contract the L/C payment is chosen rather than open account and advance payment, the documentary credit operations emerge. At this point the L/C is supposed to be considered an independent agreement from the main contract (most of the time it is sales contract). The article 4 of UCP 600 also acknowledges that a credit by its nature is a separate transaction from the sale or other contract on which it may be based. Also the article continues with the following statement which deserves a special focus: “banks are in no way is concerned with or bound by such contract, even if any reference whatsoever to it is included in the credit.” Because especially this emphasizes the imperative and strong character of the rule of independence of L/C from other contracts. According to this point, it is required to distinguish between them and not treat them as identical. At the next stage importer asks for a bank to issue a credit. And bank review the financial position of one asked for a credit issuing, then if it is confirmed, bank may issue a credit. After issuing the credit a bank sends relevant documents to a beneficiary. The beneficiary checks the requirements of L/C and if it is suitable, sends relevant goods. After sending, all of the necessary documents, such as invoice, bill of lading, insurance certificate and others, are compiled and submitted to a bank. In its turn a bank check if the documents comply with the terms of L/C. If there is not any problem with the submitted documents by the beneficiary, the bank makes a payment. If otherwise, the documents may be rejected or refused by a bank. After the payment of a bank, the documents are submitted to a importer in order to clear customs and obtain the goods. Usually Letter of Credit operations are opened within several days. In practice, especially in countries such as Uzbekistan, LC operations are widely used in import of machinery, construction materials, industrial equipment, and export of commodities like cotton and textiles, where payment risk must be strictly controlled.

While the letter of credit has been in use for centuries, the modern letter of credit is so far different as to be practically a new instrument. The early letter of credit was usually given by a principal to his agent, for use in purchasing goods abroad³. The reasons for this were twofold. In the first place, the international worldwide banks did not exist. In addition, the firms doing international trade were so few and so well-known, that the promise contained in their own letter of credit

² Justin Pritchard. (2012, August 30). *Letter of credit – How letters of credit work*.

³ Finkelstein, H. N. (1925). Performance of conditions under a letter of credit. *Columbia Law Review*, 25, 724.

was considered sufficient security for the sale of goods on credit, and the functions of the letter were chiefly to authenticate the power of the agent. It was generally addressed to a correspondent bank on which the drafts were to be drawn and requested the bank to pay such drafts as were drawn by the agent. With the rising importance and increasing complexity of this trade and the entrance of new firms into the field, the letter of credit became a necessity and took on other aspects⁴.

The origins of documentary credits trace back to the mediaeval era⁵. Although an instrument named a letter of credit is described as early as in the seventeenth century in Malynes's *lex Mercatoria*⁶, but they actually emerge from the customs of European merchants and banks, especially in Italy during the renaissance offering means to secure payment for goods transported across extensive distances⁷. In the 19th century, after the first world war, the advent of industrialization and enhanced worldwide trade due to agreement such as Bretton wood⁸, led to the formalization of banking procedures in Britain and Europe, and the need for documentary credits was felt to serve interest of merchants, bankers and trade as a whole of that time⁹.

However, at that stage there was no standard form for documentary credits nor standard regulations dealing to the issue of such credits. Each bank issued its own form of credit on the conditions it saw fit. Furthermore, the first moves towards standardizing documentary letter of credit practice came from the United States of America after the enactment of the American federal reserve act in 1913¹⁰.

As mentioned above today, there is a unified rules regulating the relations arising from letter of credit operations named "UCP 600 - Uniform Customs and Practice for Documentary Credits", which involves the whole valid process issuing and operating the L/C. These custom and practice governs all the relations between the bank and a particular party who asks to issue a credit. At the same time, as claimed before UCP 600 applies when the issue is in the sphere of bank obligations and rights. It is said that UCP 600 provides standardized rules published by the International Chamber of Commerce governing documentary credits, defining bank responsibilities and document examination standards. Under the article 5 of UCP 600, banks deal with only documents, not with goods, services or performance to which the documents may relate¹¹.

According to UCP 600¹² and at the same time well-known scholars¹³, there are different types of a documentary credit, which are:

⁴ Vagts, D. F., Dodge, W. S., Buxbaum, H. L., & Koh, H. H. (2015). *Transnational business problems* (6th ed.). Foundation Press.

⁵ Shapiro, B. (1994). The concept "fact": Legal origins and cultural diffusion. *Albion*, 26(2), 227–252.

⁶ Malynes, G. (1622). *Consuetudo, vel lex mercatoria, or the ancient law-merchant*.

⁷ Spufford, P. (2014). The provision of stable moneys by Florence and Venice, and North Italian financial innovations in the Renaissance period. In P. Bernholz & R. Vaubel (Eds.), *Explaining monetary and financial innovation: A historical analysis*. Springer.

⁸ Bretton Woods Agreement. (1944). International monetary and trade regulation agreement among 44 countries (July 1944).

⁹ Kozolchyk, B. (1979). Letters of credit. In J. S. Ziegel (Ed.), *International encyclopaedia of comparative law* (Vol. 9, Ch. 5, pp. 12–15). Martinus Nijhoff.

¹⁰ Jamil, M. (n.d.). Evaluating the role of documentary credits in international trade: Reliability, security, and practical challenges. *Journal article*.

¹¹ International Chamber of Commerce, *Uniform Customs and Practice for Documentary Credits (UCP 600)* (ICC Publishing, 2007), Article 5.

¹² International Chamber of Commerce, *Uniform Customs and Practice for Documentary Credits (UCP 600)* (ICC Publishing, 2007).

¹³ James E. Byrne, *The Official Commentary on UCP 600* (ICC Publishing, 2007).

1. Revocable or Irrevocable Letters of Credit.
2. Confirmed Credit.
3. Transferable Credit.
4. With or without Recourse Credit.
5. Revolving Letter of Credit.
6. Transit Credit.
7. Back to Back Credit.
8. The Sight Credit.
9. The Credit available against Time Draft (Usance Credit).
10. The Deferred Payment Credit.

According to some publications, it is believed Letter of credit is a bank guarantee given by the issuing bank itself in order to ensure a reliable atmosphere between parties – exporter and importer. It seems there may be a tension between these two legal instruments. Some researches can give an opinion that these two terms (Letter of Credit and Bank guarantee) are slight different from each other to some extent. For example, an Indian researcher Sankalp Jain¹⁴ argues that a letter of credit will serve as a guarantee, but even if it has that effect, it is not a guaranty. The law surrounding the guaranty arises because the guarantor promises to act for the debt, default, or miscarriage of another. That would make the guarantor secondarily obligated to the oblige should the primary obligor fail in his performance to the oblige. Letters of credit ensures that a transaction proceeds as planned while bank guarantees reduce the loss if the transaction doesn't go as planned. A letter of credit is an obligation taken on by a bank to make a payment once certain criteria are met. Once these terms are completed and confirmed, the bank will transfer the funds. This ensures the payment will be made as long as the services are performed. For example, a letter of credit can be used in the delivery of goods or the completion of a service. The seller may request that the buyer obtain a letter of credit before the transaction occurs. The buyer would purchase this letter of credit from a bank and forward it to the seller's bank. This letter would substitute the bank's credit for that of its client, ensuring correct and timely payment. A bank guarantee might be used when a buyer obtains goods from a seller then runs into cash flow difficulties and can't pay the seller.

The bank guarantee would pay an agreed upon sum to the seller. Similarly, if the supplier was unable to provide the goods, the bank would then pay the purchaser the agreed-upon sum. The bank guarantee acts as a safety measure for the opposing party in the transaction. A guaranty is a promise to answer for the debt, default or miscarriage of another.

A guarantor is making himself liable for the performance of some obligation which is owed by another person who in the first instance is liable for the payment or the performance. A guaranty is in essence an insurance or security device and not one by which a transaction is financed.

Conclusion

Letter of credits provide security for both exporters and importers by ensuring that payment is made only when the required documents are presented in compliance with the terms of the credit. However, in order to further improve the efficiency and practicality of the system, two main suggestions can be proposed. Firstly, the LC process could be improved by increasing the level of digitalization and automation in document checking and transmission.

¹⁴ Sankalp Jain, *Letter of Credit and Bank Guarantees: A Comparative Study* (Indian Journal of Legal Studies, 2018).

In many cases, delays occur due to manual verification of documents and traditional paper-based procedures. The wider use of electronic documentation and secure digital platforms would reduce processing time, minimize human error, and make LC operations faster and more efficient, especially in cross-border transactions involving countries such as Uzbekistan.

Secondly, greater harmonization and simplification of documentary requirements could significantly improve the system. In practice, discrepancies in documents are a common reason for delays or rejection of payment. If banks and trading partners applied more standardized and simplified documentation practices under UCP 600, it would reduce unnecessary disputes and increase trust between parties. This would be particularly beneficial for exporters in developing trade markets, where complex documentation often creates additional barriers.

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